

1 **TBC1D13 is activated in response to growth factor inhibition and in platinum resistance in vitro.**

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6 We describe here activation of a Tbc family gene Tbc1d13 in cells exposed to a growth factor inhibitor
7 and in cells engineered to develop resistance to chemotherapy in vitro. The data support a role for
8 Tbc1d13 in diverse contexts involving challenge or stress.

9 Citations

10 Davey, J.R., Humphrey, S.J., Junutula, J.R., Mishra, A.K., Lambright, D.G., James, D.E. and Stöckli, J.,
11 2012. TBC1D13 is a RAB35 specific GAP that plays an important role in GLUT4 trafficking in adipocytes.
12 Traffic, 13(10), pp.1429-1441.